

COMPOSITE LAMINATES WITH ENHANCED INDENTATION AND FRACTURE RESISTANCE DUE TO NEGATIVE POISSON RATIOS.

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ABSTRACT

Two different composite laminate lay up configurations have been designed with the aid of computer software, in order to have matching in-plane and flexural engineering constants but one positive and one negative in-plane Poisson ratio (ν_{xy}). The mechanical performance of both laminates has been compared via tensile testing of notched specimens and indentation testing. It was found that the laminate with a negative ν_{xy} absorbed more energy at failure in tension and had greater crack opening displacements than the conventional laminate with positive ν_{xy} . Although neither laminate possessed a negative through the thickness Poisson ratio, (ν_{xz}), the one with the lower ν_{xz} value possessed the greatest indentation resistance suggesting that this may be the case for laminates with a negative ν_{xz} .

KEY WORDS: Composite, Poisson Ratio, Fracture, Indentation, Laminate.

1. INTRODUCTION

By changing the Poisson ratio (ν) of a material it is possible to significantly alter many of the mechanical properties. It is as fundamental to the behaviour of a material as the Young's modulus. In particular, by having a large negative ν it is possible to increase the shear modulus of the material at the expense of the bulk modulus [1]. This is particularly important for many structural applications of materials such as cars, ships, aircraft, buildings, all of which are basically shell structures and where a high shear modulus is more useful than a high

bulk modulus. Other properties that may be improved by a negative ν include indentation resistance and fracture toughness.

Negative Poisson ratios have been fabricated from conventional polymeric foams [2,3,4,5], in which the effect is achieved by transforming the cellular structure into a reentrant structure. It has been shown [5] that these foams are more resilient than conventional foam materials and can be used in applications requiring improved impact resistance [4].

More recently [6,7,8] it has been shown that an expanded form of polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) may exhibit large negative ν values demonstrating that different network structures can be used to produce the negative Poisson ratio. The expanded PTFE suffers from the disadvantage of a very low modulus making it unsuitable for structural applications. However, a similar microstructure has now been fabricated in a stiff ultra high molecular weight polyethylene [9,10].

Another important application for such materials is as the sandwich material for composite sandwich panels, where the property of a negative ν may be used to fabricate doubly-curved, domed (or synclastic) panels [11].

The above examples represent cases where the property of a negative ν is produced by altering the microstructure of materials that are basically isotropic. It is, however, possible to produce similar effects in anisotropic composite laminates, with the added benefits of very high intrinsic stiffnesses and strengths. It has previously been shown, by modelling that a choice of suitable stacking sequence can induce either in-plane [12] or out of plane [13] negative ν effects. However, the design of such laminates is not a simple task. This paper describes software developed to model and optimise laminates with these properties and experiments to measure their resulting performance.

1.1 Theoretical Modelling. If we consider a symmetric angle-ply composite laminate comprising layers of continuous unidirectional glass or carbon fibre in an epoxy matrix, under axial load L (fig. 1). The major or in-plane Poisson ratio is defined as [12]

$$\nu_{xy} = \frac{-\epsilon_y}{\epsilon_x}$$

It has been shown [12] that by giving careful consideration to the stacking sequence of continuous fibre reinforced laminates, it is possible to design a laminate lay-up configuration with a negative ν_{xy} . Fig.2 shows the variation of ν_{xy} vs. the bisector of angles between two laminae for a bidirectional laminate of AS4/3501-6 carbon/epoxy. It should be noted that a small change in angle results in a large change in Poisson ratio.

So far, only a limited amount of work has been performed on laminates with negative Poisson ratios, in order to establish whether or not they have improved mechanical performance in

comparison to conventional laminates with similar properties. In reference [14] the authors have compared the fracture toughness of an unbalanced laminate with negative ν_{xy} to that of a balanced laminate with similar tensile strength but positive ν_{xy} and have attributed the improved fracture toughness of the unbalanced laminate and difference in fracture behaviour to its negative Poisson ratio.

Composite laminates with negative out-of-plane (or through-the-thickness) Poisson ratios have been modelled [13] and it has been suggested [1,2] that such laminates would have improved indentation resistance. The negative out-of-plane Poisson ratio (ν_{xz}) is caused by the high degree of normal shear coupling and the constraining influence of adjacent laminar layers. It is this coupling that results in high in-plane shear stresses.

Until recently the design of composite laminates to a prerequisite mechanical specification has been more or less a case of trial and error, design procedures being based on technical experience rather than scientific method. Software has been developed at Liverpool University which uses a design-oriented optimisation approach for the design of the most general laminated composite. No symmetry assumptions are required and all the material layers may be different [15]. The difference between the calculated properties of a laminate as given by an appropriate lamination theory, and that required by the designer is minimised subject to various constraints including stiffness and strength considerations. Various laminar sequences are iterated through until an optimum configuration, with the minimum difference between actual and required properties is found. Hence, in addition to being able to calculate the extensional, coupling and flexural stiffnesses of laminates, including the in-plane and out-of-plane Poisson ratios, for a composite laminate of any lay-up sequence, the software is also capable of designing an optimal laminate lay-up sequence to meet a particular set of desired properties and at the same time, meet other design specifications. This software is used in this paper to predict the variation in ν_{xy} with bisector angle for the bidirectional laminates shown in Fig.2.

In this study, the software has been used to design two laminate lay-up configurations with matching in-plane and flexural engineering constants but differing ν_{xy} i.e. one positive and one negative. The subsequent mechanical performance of the two different laminate configurations is then compared.

This work is intended to be a forerunner to an investigation into the improved indentation and delamination resistance obtained for laminates with negative out-of-plane Poisson ratios (ν_{xz}) when subjected to low velocity impacts in which it is intended to use the aforementioned software to optimise laminate lay-up configurations with negative ν_{xz} whilst simultaneously minimising the mismatch in in-plane ν_{xy} and coefficients of mutual influence between adjacent laminae layers which encourage delamination.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Laminate Design. Computer software was used to design two laminate lay up configurations with matching in-plane and flexural engineering constants but different in-plane Poisson ratios i.e. one positive and one negative ν_{xy} . The selected configurations were $[0,15,75,15]_S$ (negative ν_{xy}) and $[0, -70,10,25]_S$ (positive ν_{xy}). The material used to prepare these laminates was AS4/3501-6 carbon fibre/epoxy prepreg. The mechanical properties of these laminates, as predicted by the software are displayed in Table 1.

2.2 Experimental Measurement of Mechanical Properties. Tensile specimen were prepared from each laminate in accordance with BS2782 Part 3 Method 1003 and strain gauge equipment was used to determine the longitudinal modulus (E_x) and in-plane Poisson ratio (ν_{xy}) of the laminates under a tensile load. Results are shown alongside the software predicted mechanical properties in Table 1.

2.3 Fracture Toughness. Specimen geometries were prepared in accordance with BS2782 Part 3 Method 1003. Double edge notch geometries were selected with total notch lengths ranging from 2 to 12mm in intervals of 2mm. The notches were made using a fret saw to cut the bulk of the notch and then the crack tip was sharpened using a jewellers saw. A standard tensile test was performed on each specimen using an Instron 1185 tensile testing machine at 2mm/min crosshead speed and the fracture toughness of the specimens reported in terms of the energy absorbed by the specimen at failure. During the tests, the crack opening displacement (COD) was measured using an extensometer.

2.4 Indentation Tests. Specimen dimensions were in agreement with BS2782 Part 3 Method 365 D.A. A maximum load of 0.2KN was applied to the surface of the specimen via a ball indenter of 5mm diameter and travelling at 0.5mm/min so as to only apply elastic deformation to the specimen and not to introduce permanent deformation by indentation or delamination between layers. The object of these tests was to compare the indentation resistance of the two laminate lay-up configurations. The test proceedings were carried out in accordance with BS2782 Part 3 methods 365 D.A. and from the results, the reduced test load F_r corresponding to the reduced depth of impressions was calculated from the equation

$$F_r = R_m \left(\frac{hr}{h} \right)^{1.23} \times \left(\frac{50}{D} \right)^{0.63}$$

where F_m = test load, in Newtons, on indenter.

hr = reduced depth of impression = 0.08mm

h = depth of impression in millimetres

D = Diameter of ball = 5mm.

And from this,
$$H = \frac{1}{5\pi} \times \frac{Fr}{hr}$$

Indentation tests were repeated on the same area of specimen in order to try to eliminate the effect of resistance to indentation due to the matrix in the laminate alone. Further indentation tests were performed on both types of laminate in which the specimens were permanently deformed by application of a 5KN load using the same 5mm ball indenter. The hardness values of both laminates were compared at this load to monitor the effect of different ply angles in the laminate on the laminates indentation resistance, as the ball penetrated each layer of the laminate.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tables 1 and 2 show the comparison of in-plane and flexural engineering constants, respectively, for the two selected laminate lay up configurations, as predicted by the software. The variation in tensile modulus (E_x) and in-plane Poisson ratio (ν_{xy}) with laminate off axis angle are shown in figs. 3 & 4 respectively. Note from these plots that a small change in laminate off axis angle can result in a large change in E_x and ν_{xy} .

The experimentally obtained values for E_x and ν_{xy} for both laminate types, in Table 1 show excellent agreement between the predicted and measured values. The software has been successfully used to predict the mechanical properties of an angle ply composite laminate and to optimise an alternative lay-up sequence whilst maintaining similar in-plane and flexural engineering constants but altering the Poisson ratio.

3.1 Fracture Toughness Tests. Fig.5 shows the variation in crack opening displacement (COD) with notch length for the tensile specimens. The considerably higher values of COD for the [0/15/75/15]_S laminate with a negative ν_{xy} indicates that these specimens are able to undergo higher strains to failure than the conventional laminates with a positive ν_{xy} . The energies absorbed by the specimens at initial ply failure and then ultimate specimen failure are displayed in table 3. Again, the specimens with a negative ν_{xy} tend to absorb more energy before failure as a result of their ability to undergo higher strains to failure.

3.2 Indentation Tests. Results for ball indentation hardness of the two laminate configurations are presented in table 4. For the elastic response of the specimen under low load (0.2KN) the [0/-70/10/25]_S laminate with the much lower through the thickness Poisson ratio $\nu_{xz} = +0007$ had a greater resistance to indentation than the [0/15/75/15]_S laminate with $\nu_{xz} = +0.203$. This result suggests that laminates with negative ν_{xz} values would have a significantly greater resistance to indentation than conventional laminates with positive ν_{xz} values. Further work is underway to investigate this effect. The specimen hardness

values for ball indentation under a 5KN load where permanent damage results are similar for both laminate types. This suggests that the increased indentation resistance due to a reduced or negative ν_{xz} may only be an elastic effect.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Computer software has been used successfully to optimise two laminate lay-up configurations, with matching in-plane and flexural engineering constants but different in-plane Poisson ratios. It has been shown experimentally that the laminate configuration with the negative ν_{xy} has a higher fracture toughness than the conventional laminate with a positive ν_{xy} . For the indentation tests it was found that the laminate with the lower through the thickness Poisson ratio ($\nu_{xz} = 0.007$) possessed a greater indentation resistance than the laminate with $\nu_{xz} = 0.203$.

These preliminary results suggest that composite laminates designed to have either negative in-plane or out-of-plane Poisson ratios will have enhanced mechanical performance over conventional positive Poisson ratio laminates. Software is available to enable this design procedure to be performed.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank ICI Chemicals and Polymers plc for their assistance in this study. JPD is funded by the Science and Engineering Research Council, UK.

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TABLE 1. Software predictions for the material properties of the two laminate configurations and experimentally obtained values for in-plane engineering constants.

Configuration		Poissons Ratios		E_x GPa	E_y GPa	G_{xy} GPa
		ν_{xy}	ν_{xz}			
[0/15/75/15] _S	Predicted	-0.134	+0.203	63.4	27.2	6.3
	experimentally obtained	-0.116	-	61.6	-	-
[0/-70/10/25] _S	Predicted	+0.466	+0.007	60.2	25.6	8.5
	experimentally obtained	+0.465	-	61.7	-	-

TABLE 2. Software predictions for flexural engineering constants for the two laminate configurations.

Configuration	ν_{xy} Flex	E_x Flex GPa	E_y Flex GPa	G_{xy} Flex GPa
[0/15/75/15] _S	-0.002	89.2	18.4	6.2
[0/-70/10/25] _S	+0.226	80.0	24.5	6.0

TABLE 3. Energies absorbed by specimens of different notch lengths for the two laminate configurations at first ply failure, and then ultimate specimen failure.

Notch Length mm	[0/15/75/15] _s Energy Absorbed (J)		[0/-70/10/25] _s Energy Absorbed (J)	
	1st Ply Failure	Ultimate Failure	1st Ply Failure	Ultimate Failure
2	5.3	7.4	4.2	5.5
4	4.2	4.2	5.2	6.4
6	5.0	9.0	4.0	4.0
8	4.3	4.3	2.9	2.9
10	4.5	6.8	3.7	3.7
12	4.0	8.9	3.3	4.4

TABLE 4. Indentation resistance of the two laminate configurations.

Configuration	ν_{xz}	Ball Indentation Hardness Values daN mm ⁻²	
		0.2KN Load	5 KN Load
[0/15/75/15] _s	+0.203	81.4	494
[0/-70/10/25] _s	+0.007	126	479

Fig.1.

Fig.1. Angle-ply laminate under axial load L.

Fig.2. Software publications for the variation in ν_{xy} with off-axis angle in an AS4/3501-6 bidirectional laminate.

Fig.3. Software predictions for the variation in E_x with off-axis angle in $[0,15,75,15]_s$ and $[0,-70,10,25]_s$ AS4/3501-6 laminates.

Fig.4. Software predications for the variation in v_{xy} with off-axis angle in $[0,15,75,15]_S$ and $[0,-70,10,25]_S$ AS4/3501-6 laminates.

Fig.5. Variation in crack opening displacement with notch length for $[0,15,75,15]_S$ and $[0,-70,10,25]_S$ laminates.